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Innovation Through Necessity Creating a Practical Clinical Reference Booklet in Emergency Medicine and Pre Hospital Care for Medical Students in Sabah

Emergency care carries an intensity that is difficult to explain in ordinary classrooms. The moment a patient collapses in the triage area or a child arrives struggling to breathe, the environment changes its pace, and every student standing nearby feels that shift in their body. When I began supervising Diploma in Medical and Health Sciences (DMHS) students at Training Institute Ministry of Health Malaysia Kota Kinabalu (ILKKM Kota Kinabalu), I realized how strongly this atmosphere affected them. They had revised their notes, memorized the theory and passed earlier skill stations, yet the pressures of the Emergency Department often unsettled them. Their hesitation did not stem from poor ability, but from the gap between structured lecture delivery and the unpredictable realities in real setting.

I searched for a single resource that could bridge this gap, something practical enough to use during clinical teaching while still aligned with the curriculum. National guidelines existed, but their length made them difficult to consult in urgent settings. Students kept their own notes, yet these were often scattered, handwritten and organized differently from one student to another. During teaching rounds, I found myself repeating the same algorithms and dosage reminders, and I wished for a compact tool that could anchor the conversation. Out of this need, I drafted a small, laminated booklet for personal use. It contained the essential algorithms, short notes, procedures, and emergency drug references that students frequently struggled to recall under pressure. I created it quietly, without imagining that it would become anything more than a support for my own teaching.

The response from students was stronger than expected. They saw me consulting the booklet during bedside teaching skill, and one by one they began asking for their own copy. The design was simple, but the clarity helped them organize their thinking during airway assessments, triage decisions and emergency cases. They used it during practice sessions, brought it into the department and treated it as a

quick guide when confronted with a case they were unsure about. What began as personal reference slowly transformed into a pilot project in late 2023 because students themselves recognized its usefulness before I ever labelled it an innovation.

The booklet's journey continued after those students graduated. Newly appointed Assistant Medical Officers (AMO) entering the mandatory posting program, or *Program Penempatan Wajib (PPW)*, often describe their first 6 months in the Emergency Department as a period filled with both excitement and fear. They are suddenly required to perform at a higher level, manage unstable patients and work alongside senior AMOs and doctors with minimal room for hesitation. Many of my former students carried the booklet into their PPW rotations, and their colleagues including nurses and doctors quickly noticed. Requests began coming through personal messages, followed by orders from other districts and eventually other states. It travelled from Kota Kinabalu to hospitals in Sabah, Sarawak, Labuan and later to peninsular Malaysia where Sabah graduates were placed. The spread was organic, driven entirely by word of mouth and the daily realities students faced in busy emergency units.

Today, more than 1500 copies have been sold, and the booklet is registered with an ISBN. Its growth has been shaped as much by the users as by the initial concept. Senior AMOs reached out highlighted changes to national algorithms. Specialists pointed out small refinements that improved clarity and safety. Each round of feedback guided an update, and the booklet evolved into a more accurate and academically grounded tool. This iterative process reflects the spirit of action research, where cycles of use, reflection and revision strengthen the relevance of an educational resource over time.

What became clearer to me through this innovation is the way educational equity plays out quietly in clinical training. A simple, affordable, pocket-sized booklet helps reduce the unevenness of preparation among students. It does not replace the lecturer's role, but it gives students a dependable reference at moments when their mind goes blank or senior guidance is momentarily unavailable. For early stage AMOs in PPW who are still finding their confidence, that small booklet often serves as a psychological anchor as much as a clinical one.

Innovation in education is sometimes described in technological terms, yet this booklet showed me that innovation can emerge from closely observing what students struggle with and responding in a way that fits their context. The Emergency Department in Sabah demands clarity, confidence and readiness from students, and the booklet was created to support precisely those needs. It may not look sophisticated, but its value lies in being accessible, portable and immediately usable in high stakes situations.

When I look back, the booklet's origin feels almost accidental, yet its evolution reflects a collective effort between lecturers, students and clinicians who share the same goal of preparing young medical workers for the realities of emergency care. What began as a quiet attempt to make my own teaching easier has grown into a widely used resource that continues to evolve alongside the practice it serves. It remains, at its core, an expression of necessity shaped into innovation, grounded in the everyday learning experiences of students who carry it into the emergency bay as they begin their journey as Assistant Medical Officers.

Written by Melvin Ebin Bondi

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